

Insect resistance

Varietal resistance to the brown planthopper *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) and its biotypes

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IR26, bred for resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stal) at the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI), was introduced into Kerala after a 1973–74 BPH outbreak and was found to be susceptible there. Confirmation of that finding from various stations in India and Sri Lanka indicated the existence of a BPH biotype different from that at IRRI, and led to the study of Indian biotypes.

In 1975, varieties from the International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery (IRBPHN) were screened for resistance to separate BPH cultures from Hyderabad and Pantnagar. First-

and second-instar nymphs were released on 10-day-old seedlings, whose reactions were scored on a 0–9 scale (0 = no damage; 9 = complete kill) when more than 95 percent of Taichung Native 1 (TN1) (susceptible control) plants were killed (see table).

Ptb 33 and ARC 6650 were reportedly resistant at Hyderabad (M. B. Kalode, 1976) and at Pattambi (B. Thomas, 1976). We also found ARC 6650 highly resistant to the Hyderabad culture. However, when it was screened for resistance to the Pantnagar culture, it scored 5.5; all the plants later succumbed to BPH damage. Gangala also reacted differently to the Hyderabad and Pantnagar cultures.

The differential reactions of ARC 6650, Gangala, and Ptb 33 to BPH strongly suggest the existence of different biotypes in India. This possibility is being investigated.

Brown planthopper damage in Sri Lanka

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Widespread infestations by the brown planthopper frequently destroy crops in Sri Lanka. In 1974 about 400 ha were damaged even though sprayed with agrochemicals by helicopter. The use of resistant H-501, BG 11/11 has been considered effective, but not entirely. In my own research I find that varieties with wide leaves and thick stems are more susceptible. Lines with a large number of silica cells have been found more resistant. The breeding of varieties containing much silica should receive more attention.

Brown planthopper outbreak in Bangladesh

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The brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* was first definitely recorded in Bangladesh in 1969, but its presence in undivided Bengal since 1917 is suggested by synonyms. A 1957 report also indicated the pest's presence.

In Bangladesh, the first outbreak of BPH occurred in April–May, 1976, on boro (November–May) rice crops near Dacca city. IR8 and BR 3 fields of about 4 ha were burned in patches. The crops were in milky to hard-dough stage. Pajam II was free of infestation. The weather was dry, but the affected plots had standing sewage water. The hopperburned plots had 100 to 200 insects per hill. A second outbreak occurred in October, 1976, at the BRRI farm on the aman (July–December) crop of BR 3 which has luxuriant growth and heavy foliage. The affected plots had standing irrigation water, although the weather was mainly dry. Heavy BPH infestation (1,000 to 2,000 insects/hill) was accompanied by hopperburn. Adjacent plots with variety BR 4 also had heavy BPH populations.

Reaction of rice varieties to the brown planthopper in India.

Variety/germ plasm	Resistant gene	Reaction ^a	
		Pantnagar	Hyderabad
Andaraghawewa	<i>Bph 1</i>	8.5	9
Dalwa Sannam (Mtu 15)	"	9.0	9
Thella Gerikasanavari (SLO 12)	"	9.0	9
Ptb 21	"	8.8	8.5
RP 9-6	"	8.8	8.3
IR26	"	9.0	8.5
C 62-1-373	<i>bph 2</i>	7.8	7.7
ASD 7	"	9.0	9.0
H 5	"	7.0	9.0
Murungakayan 3	"	9.0	9.0
Murungakayan 101b	"	8.5	9.0
Murungakayan 303b	"	8.8	8.6
Palisithari 601	"	8.6	8.0
Ptb 19	?	8.5	8.3
Chianung-Sen-yu 11	?	9.0	9.0
Co 9	?	9.0	9.0
ARC 6650	?	5.5	0.2
Muthumanikarn	?	9.0	9.0
C 62-1-230	?	7.5	9.0
Gangala	?	8.5	5.5
Ptb 33	?	4.0 ^b	R ^c
TN1	—	9.0	9.0

^aReaction score based on a 1–9 scale: 0 = no damage, 9 = complete kill.

^bScore based on 3 plants.

^cReported from Hyderabad as resistant.